

STUDY ON POSTBUCKLING BEHAVIOR OF DELAMINATED STIFFENED COMPOSITE PLATES

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ABSTRACT: The postbuckling behavior of stiffened composite laminates with delamination damage under uniform compression is investigated by finite element method. The linear and non-linear finite element formulae for both laminated face and stiffener are constructed on the basis of the Mindlin first order shear effect theory and Von-Karman non-linearity deformation assumption. The kinetics relation at the delamination front is applied to join the delaminated and perfect structures together. By some numerical examples, the influences of the distribution of the stiffeners, the location of the delamination and the boundary conditions of the plates upon postbuckling behavior of the stiffened composite laminate are discussed.

KEY WORDS: postbuckling behavior, delamination damage, low energy impact, stiffened laminated plates, numerical simulation

INTRODUCTION

Stiffened laminated plate is a most common structure component of the modern ships, submarines, planes and aircrafts due to its advantages including high weight-stiffness ratio, weight-strength ratio, etc., as a result, study on its failure mechanisms has been of great concern for a long time. Delamination is the most critical damage to the laminates, which can be generated by imperfect curing, low impact, etc. which happens very often. As a matter of fact, the delamination can dramatically decrease the strength and stability of the structure, especially, for compressive and shear loading cases. Therefore, to analyze and predict the residual strength and load capacity of stiffened laminated plates is a significant engineering subject needs to be solved urgently, and the profound investigation about this problem will make a farther improvement of the fundamental research and application of composite laminated structures.

An extensive study on the bare delaminated plate has been made in recent years by several researchers [1-5], that are satisfied by the requests for engineering in designing and analyzing such structures. However, to construct the experimental and numerical simulation models and develop corresponding analysis methods of the delaminated plates would be more difficult and complicated yet for the stiffened laminated plates with damages. As Greenhagh et al. [6] has emphasized that, the damage characteristic of stiffened laminated plate is different from that of the bare plate, so the experiment data and numerical results obtained from bare plate can not be used to analyze the stiffened laminated plates. The stiffened plate will not only contain the damages which can be found in the bare plate, but also has some special modes damage, such as the debonding between the stiffener and base plate etc. Thus, the behavior of delaminated stiffened plates is still not clear up to date and few papers have been published in the open literature [7-13].

The objective of this paper is to develop a numerical simulation model and method to investigate the postbuckling behavior of stiffened composite laminates with delamination under uniform compression load. The linear and non-linear finite element formulae for both laminated face and eccentric stiffener are constructed on the basis of the Mindlin first order shear effect theory and Von-Karman non-linearity deformation assumption. The continuity of the displacements and rotations along the delamination front strictly applied to join all parts of the structures. By some numerical

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examples, the influences of the distribution of the stiffeners, the location of the delamination and the boundary conditions of the plates upon the postbuckling behavior of the stiffened composite laminate are discussed.

MODELIZATION AND FORMULAE OF FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

A stiffened composite laminated plate is simulated by combination of plate element and beam element. The plate panels are idealized by plate element and the stiffeners are idealized as beam. Both kinds of the linear and non-linear elements formulae are established on basis of the first-order shear theory and Von-Karman linear deformation assumption.

1. Nonlinear strain-displacement relationships

According to the Reissner-Mindlin plate theory, the displacement fields for the plate and the beam element can be expressed as follows:

For the plate element:

$$\begin{aligned} u &= u_0(x, y) + z\theta_y(x, y) \\ v &= v_0(x, y) - z\theta_x(x, y) \\ w &= w_0(x, y) \end{aligned} \quad \bullet 1 \bullet$$

For the beam element:

$$\begin{aligned} u &= u_c(x) + z\theta_y(x) \\ v &= -z\theta_x(x) \\ w &= w_c(x) \end{aligned} \quad \bullet 2 \bullet$$

Where u_0 , v_0 and w_0 denote the mid-plane translational displacements along the x -, y - and z -directions of the plate, u_c and w_c denote the mid-plane translational displacements along the x - and z -directions of the beam, respectively; while θ_x and θ_y are the rotations of the cross-section along the x -axis and y -axis.

Using the von-Karman strains for moderate rotations, the non-linear strain-displacement equations are formulated as follows:

$$\{\varepsilon\}^T = \{\varepsilon_l\}^T + \{\varepsilon_n\}^T \quad \bullet 3 \bullet$$

where $\{\varepsilon_0\}^T$ and $\{\varepsilon_l\}^T$ are the linear and Von-Karman non-linear strain vectors, respectively, in for the plate element:

$$\{\varepsilon_l\}^T = \left\{ u_{,x}^0 \quad v_{,y}^0 \quad u_{,y}^0 + v_{,x}^0 \quad z\theta_{y,x} \quad -z\theta_{x,y} \quad -z\theta_{x,x} + z\theta_{y,y} \quad w_{,y} - \theta_x \quad w_{,x} + \theta_y \right\}^T$$

for the beam element:

$$\{\varepsilon_l\}^T = \left\{ \varepsilon_x \quad \gamma_{xy} \quad \gamma_{xz} \right\}^T = \left\{ u_{c,x} + z\theta_{y,x} \quad -z\theta_{x,x} \quad w_{c,x} + \theta_y \right\}^T$$

$$\{\varepsilon_n\}^T = \left\{ w_{c,x}^2/2 \quad 0 \quad 0 \right\}^T$$

2. Formulations of finite element

Define $\{d\}_P^e = \{u_0 \quad v_0 \quad w_0 \quad \theta_x \quad \theta_y\}_P^T$, to construct a plate element with four-nodes, the corresponding displacement vector $\{d\}_P^e$ can be expressed as

$$\{d\}_P^e = [N]_P \{\delta\}_P^e \quad \bullet 4 \bullet$$

Where $\{\delta\}_P^e = \{u_{0i} \quad v_{0i} \quad w_{0i} \quad \theta_{xi} \quad \theta_{yi}\}_P^T$ ($i=1\sim 4$) is its nodal displacement vector, and $[N]_P$ is the bi-linear interpolation shape function matrix.

Define $\{d\}_s^e = \{u_0 \quad w_0 \quad \theta_x \quad \theta_y\}_s^T$, to establish a beam element with three-nodes, the corresponding displacement vector $\{d\}_s^e$ can be written as

$$\{d\}_s^e = [N]_s \{\delta\}_s^e \quad \bullet 5 \bullet$$

Where $\{\delta\}_s^e = \{u_{0i} \ w_{0i} \ \theta_{xi} \ \theta_{yi}\}_s^T$ ($i=1\sim 3$) is its nodal displacement vector, and $[N]_s$ is the quadratic interpolation shape function matrix. Substituting Eqs. (4) and (5) into Eq. (3) the tangent stiffness matrix of the plate and beam element can be deduced by the principle of virtual work and selecting integral scheme, respectively. The uniform expression of the tangent stiffness matrix for the both can be obtained as follows:

$$[K_T] = [K_0] + [K_L] + [K_\sigma] \quad \bullet 6 \bullet$$

Here $[K_0]$, $[K_L]$ and $[K_\sigma]$ are the linear, non-linear incremental stiffness matrixes and geometrical stiffness matrix as the following formulations:

$$\begin{aligned} K_0 &= \int_v [B_{L0}]^T [D] [B_{L0}] |J| d\xi d\eta \\ K_L &= \int_v \left([B_{L1}]^T [D] [B_{L0}] + [B_{L0}]^T [D] [B_{L1}] + [B_{L1}]^T [D] [B_{L1}] \right) |J| d\xi d\eta \\ K_\sigma &= \int_v [G]^T [M] [G] |J| d\xi d\eta \end{aligned}$$

in which $[B_{L0}]$, $[B_{L1}]$ and $[D]$ are the linear, non-linear strain-displacement and elastic matrices corresponding to plate and beam, respectively.

From some numerical testing, it can be proved the elements have superior in precision and convergence [9-10].

3. Connection between the plate and the stiffer

Assume the stiffener being attached to the upper surface of the plate panel (as shown in Fig.1). Based on the conditions of displacement compatibility along their line of connection, the displacement vector of the beam at node C of the mid-plane can be denoted by that of the plate at node O of the mid-plane:

$$\{\delta\}_c = \lambda \{\delta\}_0 \quad \bullet 7 \bullet$$

Furthermore, the relationship between the nodal displacement vectors of the beam and element referring to mid-planes of themselves are

$$\{\delta\}_s^e = [T] \{\delta\}_p^e \quad \bullet 8 \bullet$$

In Eqs. (7) and (8),

$$\lambda = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & e \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad [T] = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda & & & & \\ & \lambda & & & \\ & & \lambda & & \\ & & & \lambda & \\ & & & & \lambda \end{bmatrix}$$

Fig.1 Connection of the stiffener and plate and e is the distance between the mid-planes of stiffener and plate. Thus, the stiffness matrix $[K]$ and the equivalent nodal force $\{P\}$ of the beam element can be deduced as:

$$[K'] = [T]^T [K] [T] \quad \bullet 9 \bullet$$

$$\{P'\} = [T]^T \{P\} \quad \bullet 10 \bullet$$

4. Delamination model

Let a typical stiffened composite laminated plate contain a circular or elliptical delamination. The plate is divided into three parts: upper sub-plate, lower sub-plate and base plate denoted by 1, 2 and 3 respectively. The continuity of the displacements and rotations along the delamination front must be strictly satisfied, hence the constraint equations imposed can be written as:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} w &= w_1 = w_2 = w_3 \\ \theta_x &= \theta_{x1} = \theta_{x2} = \theta_{x3} & \theta_y &= \theta_{y1} = \theta_{y2} = \theta_{y3} \\ u_1 &= u_3 + \theta_y (H - h_u)/2 & u_2 &= u_3 - \theta_y h_u/2 \\ v_1 &= v_3 - \theta_x (H - h_u)/2 & v_2 &= u_3 + \theta_x h_u/2 \end{aligned} \right\} \bullet 11 \bullet$$

Where H and h_u denote the thickness of the base plate and the upper sub-plate, respectively.

5. The governing equation and solution procedure

Applying the principle of virtual work gives the non-linear governing equation of the stiffened composite laminate plate

$$(K_T + K'_T)\Delta q = \Delta P - R_s - R'_s \bullet 12 \bullet$$

Where K_T and K'_T are the tangent stiffness matrices of the plates and stiffeners, Δq and ΔP are the incremental displacement and load vectors; and R_s and R'_s denote the react forces of the plates and stiffeners, respectively;

The nonlinear Eq.(12) can be solved by a modified Newton-Raphson iterative scheme. At the initial step, a virtual transverse load is applied at the center of the delaminated region to initiate transverse deflections of the delaminated plates, and the disturb forces should be take out, as soon as postbuckling occurs. To prevent the upper sub-plate embedding into the lower sub-plate in the delamination region a virtual truss element, called GAP element^[14], has been used for postbuckling analysis.

BUCKLING AND POSTBUCKLING MODES OF STIFFENED PLATES WITH A DELAMINATION

Observing from the experimental studies finds the delamination configuration and size, stiffness ratio of the stiffener and base plate, and the distribution of the stiffener, etc. play very essential roles on the buckling and postbuckling modes of stiffened delaminated plates. Fig.2 summarizes three kinds of typical buckling and postbuckling modes, namely, local, mixed and total, which can be happened between the stiffeners, across the stiffeners and in the two sides of a stiffener with double waves, respectively. The real lines in the figure denote the locations of the stiffeners. Generally, the modes (a), (b) and (c) often occur in the case of plates with strong stiffeners, because the strong sustentation given by the stiffeners results in the warp being confined only in the base plate between the two stiffeners; The modes (d), (e) and (f) usually occur in the weak stiffeners case, the reason is the stiffeners can not gives a enough support for the base plate, hence the stiffeners will buckle together with the base plate; While (g), (h) and (i) are the special modes for the cases of the stiffener being located at middle of the delamination and along the x- or y-axis. It should be noted, the geometric non-linear effect must be considered for both of stiffener and base plate during the finite element postbuckling analysis in the cases (d– i), because the stiffeners as well as the buckled part of base plate behave large deformation with load increasing.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES AND DISCUSSION

Consider a stiffened composite laminate plate embedded a central elliptical delaminations, that are simply or clamped supports along the four edges and subjected to external uniform compression load in the x -direction. The stiffeners are distributed on the x -axis. The dimensions for the plate are $L=200\text{mm}$, $a=60\text{mm}$ and $b=40\text{mm}$. The stacking sequence of the laminated plate and stiffener are $[0/90/90/0]_{4s}$ and $[0]_{64}$, respectively. The thickness of lamina $t=0.125\text{mm}$ and its mechanical properties are: $E_1=181\text{GPa}$ • $E_2=10.5\text{GPa}$ • $G_{12}=G_{13}=7.17\text{GPa}$ • $G_{23}=4.17\text{Pa}$ and $\nu_{12}=0.28$. The influences of geometric non-linear characteristic, stiffness and location of the stiffener as well as boundary condition of the stiffened delaminated plate upon its postbuckling behavior are discussed by the following numerical examples.

1. Influence of geometric non-linear characteristic of stiffeners

Let the dimensions of the stiffener $h=4\text{mm}$ and $t_s=4\text{mm}$, and the normalized external compressive load $P/P_{cr}=5.0$, in which P_{cr} is the critical load of bare plate with the same dimensions. Fig.3 plots the curves of displacement w along the stiffener of delaminated plates with 3 kinds of delamination depths: $\bar{h} = h_u/H = 4/32$ • $8/32$ and $16/32$. The mark 1 • 2 • 3 and 1' • 2' • 3' on the curves present the results with and without considering geometric non-linear characteristic of the stiffener, respectively. From the figure, it can be seen that the postbuckling behavior of the stiffened delaminated plate relies upon its delamination depths, when the stiffeners are located in the delamination region. The reason would be that, the variation of the delamination depth alters the local stiffness of the sub-plates in the delamination region and the eccentricity of the external load to the middle plane of sub-plates, which result in change of postbuckling behavior. Furthermore, by comparing with the results for the plates with three kinds of delamination depth, it is pointed out that the influence of geometric non-linear characteristic for both base plates and stiffeners must be considered for postbuckling analysis except $\bar{h} = 8/32$ case.

Fig.3 The displacements w along the stiffener with and without considering non-linearity

2. Influence of stiffness of stiffeners

Fig.4 plots the curves of midpoint displacement w of the stiffener with different height $h=4\text{mm}$ and $h=8\text{mm}$, and the same thickness $t_s=4\text{mm}$. The other dimensions and the normalized external compressive of the plate are the same as above example. The curves marked with 1 • 2 • 3 and 4 denote the results in the cases of 4 kinds of delamination depth: $\bar{h} = h_u/H = 4/32$ • $8/32$, $16/32$ and $20/32$, respectively. Analyzing the figures, it can be seen that the postbuckling behavior of the plates relates to the values of \bar{h} . For example, the displacement w decreases with increasing the stiffener height in

the first case ($\bar{h}=4/32$); On the contrary, the increasing stiffener height led to the decreasing displacement w in the other cases ($\bar{h}=8/32, 16/32$ and $20/32$). The reason would be that, the increasing the stiffener height not only improves the ability of against buckling and postbuckling of the plate, however, but also increases the eccentricity of the external load to the middle plane and changes the middle plane locations of the upper, lower sub-plates and base plate, which induces the stiffened delaminated plates to buckle easily.

3. Influence of stiffener located outside delamination region

Fig.4 The curves of midpoint displacement w of the stiffeners with different height

Fig.5-a and 5-b illustrate the curves of the midpoint displacement w of the plate with different delamination depths of $\bar{h}=4/32$ and $\bar{h}=16/32$, respectively. The figure shows the variation with normalized loads P/P_{cr} . The distances of the stiffeners are $d/L=1/2, 2/3$ and $5/6$ and their locations are out of the delamination region. The stiffener dimensions $t_s=4\text{mm}$ and $h=8\text{mm}$. The curves marked with 1, 2, 3 and 1', 2', 3' denote the results of the midpoint displacement of upper and lower sub-plates for above three kinds of different distances of the stiffeners, respectively.

Fig.5 The midpoint displacements of the plates with different delamination locations versus the normalized loads

It is clearly seen that the postbuckling mode of the plates with different distance of the stiffeners behaves the same mixed mode in the case of shallow delamination $\bar{h}=4/32$, namely, both the upper sub-plate and the lower sub-plate buckle toward the opposite direction, while in the case of deeper delamination $\bar{h}=16/32$, the postbuckling mode of the three kinds of the plates are the same total mode, it means that the upper sub-plate and lower sub-plate keep contact and buckle toward the same direction with increasing load; As the stiffener's location closes to the delamination, the midpoint displacements w in the lower sub-plate increases, but that in upper sub-plate decreases for shallow delamination, while for deeper delamination, the midpoint deformations w of the upper and lower sub-plates decrease, simultaneously.

4. Influence of boundary condition

Let dimensions of the stiffener $t_s=4\text{mm}$ and $h=8\text{mm}$, and the distance between the stiffeners

$d/L=1/2$. The boundary conditions of the plates are simply and clamped supports, respectively. The curves of the midpoint displacements w of the upper sub-plate versus the normalized loads for the plate of $H=8\text{mm}$ and $\bar{h}=4/64$ are shown in Fig.6-a, in which curves marked with 1 and 2 denote the results of the plates with the clamped and simply supports, respectively. The figure demonstrates that the displacement w for the simply supported plate is slightly larger than that of clamped plate. Because the buckling and postbuckling behavior for the plates with a shallow dilamination only posses of localization, thus the effect of the boundary conditions of the plates can be ignored. Fig.6-b shows the corresponding results for the plate of $H=4\text{mm}$ and $\bar{h}=4/32$. From the figure, it can be found that as increasing load, the midpoint displacements w for the simply supported plate is evidently larger than that for the clamped plate. Because the delamination location in the plate is closer to the middle plane of the plate than that in the former plate, thus the influence of boundary condition upon the buckling and postbuckling behavior of the stiffened delaminated plate depends on the relative delamination depth \bar{h} .

Fig.6 The midpoint displacements w of the plates with different boundary conditions versus the normalized loads

Fig.7 illustrates the displacements w in the $y=0$ section the plates ($H=4\text{ mm}$ and $\bar{h}=4/32$) with different boundary conditions, in which the marks 1, 1' and 2, 2' on the curve denote the results of upper and lower sub-plates in the normalized loading stages of $P/P_{cr}=1.5$ and $P/P_{cr}=3.0$, respectively.

Fig.7 The midpoint displacements w along the $y=0$ section for the plate with different boundary conditions load

It can be seen that the buckling and postbuckling mode of the plate with clamped support in the two loading stages posses of the same as local mode as shown in Fig.7-a ; While the mode of the plate

with simply support is the mixed mode at the first loading stage; then transfers into the total mode in the second loading stage, as show in Fig.7-b. That is an evident that the buckling and postbuckling mode rely upon the boundary condition of the plates, significantly.

CONCLUSIONS

To get a better understanding of the failure mechanism of the stiffened delaminated plates after low velocity impact, a finite element analysis model and a corresponding numerical method are developed in the paper. From discussions of a variety of numerical examples, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Strengthening method by stiffeners can efficiently improve the ability of the delaminated plate against postbuckling, however, the buckling and postbuckling behavior much more complicated than that of the bare delaminated plates.
2. The influence of geometric non-linearity of the both plates and stiffeners on the postbuckling behavior for the stiffened delaminates plate must be considered, simultaneously, especially, for the stiffeners being located in the delamination region.
3. The postbuckling behavior, namely, mode, path and the values of displacement etc. relate to the delamination size, configuration and locations, the height and distribution of the stiffeners, and the boundary condition of the plates. However, the boundary effect of the stiffened plate with a shallow and small delamination can be ignored, i.e., which postbuckling behavior possess of localization.

The study on damage growth of the stiffened composite plates with a delamination will be published another paper by authors.

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